

transplanted irrigated rice during 1987 wet season (kharif).

Soil was red sandy loam (Alfisols), with pH 6.7, 0.031% available N, 10.9 kg available P/ha, 171 kg K/ha, and cation exchange capacity of 12.6 meq/100 g. Rice varieties were Rasi (120 d) and Mandya Vijaya (145 d).

LGU was applied by broadcasting on drained soil. Prilled urea (PU) was applied according to recommended practice in the area (50% broadcast and incorporated 3-4 h before planting, 25% broadcast without incorporation at tillering, and 25% broadcast at panicle initiation).

Ammonia volatilization loss was measured in the field by direct trapping procedure and leaching loss was measured by periodically inserting leaching tubes (with microporous ceramic base) below the rooting zone, 30 cm deep to collect leachate for determining ammoniacal and nitrate N. Cumulative loss of ammoniacal N and nitrate N was computed on the basis of

Rice yield as affected by LSU/LGU.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)		Total N uptake (kg/ha) in grain + straw		Cumulative loss of Fertilizer N ^b (kg/ha)
	Rasi	Mandya Vijaya	Rasi	Mandya Vijaya	
Control, no N	2.0	3.7	43	56	—
LSU/LGU, all basal	4.8	5.3	94	126	24
PU in 3 splits (recommended practice of 50-25-25 at planting, tillering, PI)	4.5	5.4	95	112	28
LSU/LGU in 2 splits (66-34 at planting and tillering)	5.1	5.8	136	129	20
LSU/LGU in 3 splits (50-25-25 at planting, tillering, PI)	4.9	5.5	105	117	19
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.3			
CV (%)	7.5	7.5			

^aN rate is 100 kg N/ha. All treatments received 22 kg P and 41 kg K/ha. ^b Through volatilization and leaching.

percolation loss of water using drum culture technique.

Application of LSU/ LGU in two splits increased yield significantly in both varieties (see table). This appeared to be due mainly to better uptake of N by the plant and lower loss of fertilizer

N through volatilization and leaching. Three splits of LSU/LGU did not show any advantage over two splits. LSU/ LGU applied all basal did not show any significant reduction in yield from PU applied in three splits. □

Synergistic effect of organic manure and N fertilizer on irrigated rice

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We evaluated the efficiency of N source and method of application in irrigated rice KS-282 in a field experiment.

Soil was Typic Camborthids, sandy clay loam in texture having pH 7.9, ECe

0.70 dS/m and CEC 7.8 mmol (I)/ 100 g. Organic matter was 0.52%; N content 0.04%. Plot size was 16 m² and plant spacing 20 × 20 cm in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. All plots received 40 kg PK/ha.

Urea supergranules (USG) and prilled urea (PU) were compared with *S. aculeata* and *S. rostrata* as green manure and barnyard manure (BM) in combination with PU. N rate was 87 kg/ ha for each source.

USG was superior in all respects (see table). *S. rostrata* + PU was statistically equivalent to USG. Growth and yield of rice were low with *S. aculeata* + PU, and BM + PU compared to PU alone, but N recovery from PU alone was the lowest of all sources. □

Effect of organic manure and N fertilizer on growth and yield of irrigated rice.^a

Treatment ^b	Plant height (cm)	Tillers/m ²	Grain (t/ha)	Straw (t/ha)	Agronomic efficiency (kg rice/kg N)	N recovery (%)
Control(no N)	80 c	239 d	3.7 c	4.4 e	—	—
USG	95 a	340 a	5.7 a	7.8 a	23.1	54
PU	87 b	266 cd	5.3 b	7.0 c	18.4	46
<i>S. aculeata</i> + PU	86 b	298 bc	5.2 b	6.5 d	17.2	48
<i>S. rostrata</i> + PU	89 b	307 ab	5.6 a	7.3 b	21.5	52
Barnyard manure + PU	88 b	261 d	5.1 b	7.1 bc	16.7	48
SE	2	11	0.06	0.08		

^aIn a column, any 2 means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level by LSD test. ^b N source applied at 40 kg N/ha.

Effect of zincated diammonium phosphate (Zn-DAP) on rainfed lowland rice

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We studied the effect of different grades of Zn-DAP on grain yield of IR50 in wet season (kharif) 1985 and summer 1986. Soils were clay loam with pH 7.5 and 7.9, low DTPA-Zn (0.7 and 1.1 ppm) and organic C (0.21 and 0.34%), low available N (234.5 and 210.6 kg/ha), and high available P (38.5 and 40 kg/ha) and K (325.6 and 316.9 kg/ha).